

Table 1. Reaction* of some susceptible and resistant check varieties to 7 BPH populations in the Mekong Delta, Tiengiang, Vietnam, 1991.

Variety	Gene for resistance	BPH population													
		Chau Thanh, Tiengiang		Longho, Cuulong		Chauthanh, Bentre		Caolan, Dongthap		Thoaison, Angiang		Gionggieng, Kiengiang		Baclieu, Minhhai	
		Score ^b	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction
TN1	None	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S	9.0	S
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	7.6	S	5.6	S	7.6	S	7.6	S	7.0	S	7.6	S	7.6	S
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>	7.6	S	7.6	S	8.3	S	7.0	S	7.0	S	8.3	S	8.3	S
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>	5.6	S	5.0	MS	6.3	S	5.6	S	5.0	MS	7.0	S	6.3	S
Ptb 33	<i>bph2, Bph 3</i>	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R	1.0	R

*R = resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bScore = av of 3 replications.

Table 2. Reaction* of some susceptible and resistant check varieties to BPH biotypes in Asia and the Mekong Delta, Vietnam.

Variety	Gene for resistance	IRRI, Philippines ^b			Bangladesh ^b	Sri Lanka ^b	India ^b		Mekong Delta, Vietnam ^c
		Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3			Hyderabad	Cuttack	
TN1	None	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
Ptb 33	<i>bph 2, Bph 3</i>	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
ARC10550	<i>bph 5</i>	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	-

*R = resistant, S = susceptible. ^bData from O. Mochida and E. A. Heinrichs, 1980. ^cData from N. L. Chau, Nguyen Cong Thuat, and Vu Thi Chai, 1991.

Rice resistance to leafhopper (LF) in tidal wetlands

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We field-tested 22 promising lines for resistance to LF in the tidal wetlands of Tarantang, South Kalimantan, during the 1991-92 wet season.

Seedlings of each line were transplanted 21 d after seeding at 25 × 25-cm spacing in a 20-m² plot with three replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. We evaluated LF damage 45 d after transplanting.

Line IR24637-38-2-2 is resistant and other lines are moderately resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising lines to LF. Tarantang, South Kalimantan, Indonesia, 1991-92 wet season.

Line	Score ^a	Reaction ^b	Line	Score ^a	Reaction ^b
IR24637-38-2-2	1	R	IR13426-19-2	3	MR
IR21567-9-2-2-3-1-3	3	MR	IR11288-B-B-69-1	3	MR
IR31429-14-2-3	3	MR	B5344-Sm-61-2-1	3	MR
IR31432-7-2	3	MR	B5332-3d-Mr-2-4	3	MR
IR51500-AC9-7	3	MR	B6992d-99-KA-2	3	MR
IR9884-54-3-1E-P1	3	MR	IR33353-64-1-3-1	3	MR
IR15865-430-3-1-3	3	MR	IR36	5	S

^aScored using 0-9 scale of *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Reaction of IR varieties to the brown planthopper (BPH) population in Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Twenty-one IR varieties were tested against a BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*

population in a glasshouse at Raipur in 1991.

Ten-d-old seedlings of those varieties, susceptible check TN1, resistant check PTB33, and ASD7 and Mudgo were infested with 4- to 6-d-old BPH nymphs. We rated the injury of each seedling when more than 90% of the TN1 were dead.

Only IR62 and IR64 are resistant, IR34, IR36, and IR56 are moderately